

Synthesis of some Halogenonitrophenyl and Naphthyl Esters of *NN*-Diethyldithiocarbamic Acid as Potential Fungicides

Davendra Mohanlal Garg

Di- and trinitrophenyl esters of *N*-substituted dithiocarbamic acids have been reported to possess strong fungicidal activity, particularly, against *Sclerotinia fructicola*¹ and have been recommended as a spray against scurf (*Fusicladium dendriticum* Fekl.), peronospora of the grape wine (*Plasmopara viticola*, Berl & Toni), and the dry rot of potatoes². These show weak insecticidal activity against *Musca domestica* and weak acaricidal effect on the females of *Tetranychus urticae* Koch³. These are also recommended as rubber vulcanisation accelerators^{3,4}.

As halogens are known to modify biological activity of organic molecule, it seemed of interest to synthesise some analogues of these compounds containing halogens in various positions in the ring and to screen them for fungicidal, insecticidal, acaricidal, and ovicidal activities. In addition, some naphthyl and tolyl esters have also been prepared.

These compounds have been prepared by the condensation of halogeno di- and trinitrobenzenes with sodium salt of *NN*-diethyldithiocarbamic acid (Table I). In the case of trihalogenodinitrobenzenes, only one of the halogen reacted when molecular quantities of the halogenonitrobenzene and sodium salt of *NN*-diethyldithiocarbamic acid were used.

1,2,5-Tribromo-4,6-dinitrobenzene, which has two reactive halogen atoms (in 1 and 5), when condensed with sodium salt of *NN*-diethyldithiocarbamic acid, can afford two isomeric esters, 3,6-dibromo-2,4-dinitro- and 3,4-dibromo-2,6-dinitrophenyl ester of the dithiocarbamic acid, depending on whether halogen atom at position 1 or 5 has taken part in the condensation. Only one isomer, however, could be isolated and this has been found to be identical with the compound obtained from 1-chloro-2,5-dibromo-4,6-dinitrobenzene. Therefore it is 3,6-dibromo-2,4-dinitrophenyl ester of *NN*-diethyldithiocarbamic acid.

Similarly, 1,2,5-trichloro- and 2,5-dichloro-1-bromo-4,6-dinitrobenzenes furnished identical products, proved to be 3,6-dichloro-3,4-dinitrophenyl ester of *NN*-diethyldithiocarbamic acid.

A few selected compounds were tested for their antifungal and antibacterial activity in the Antibiotic Division of the Central Drug Research Institute, Lucknow,

1. Krsek and Stota, *Coll. Czech. Chem. Comm.*, 1963, 28, 3159.

2. Anonym., D. E. B. Pat. 748413.

3. Cadwell, U. S. Pat. 1726467, 1726448; *Chem. Abstr.*, 1939, 23, 5353.

4. Cadwell, *Canad. Pat.*, 3178442; *Chem. Abstr.*, 1932, 26, 1290.

TABLE I
Halogensubstituted naphthyl and naphthyl esters of N,N'-diethylglutarcamic acid.

Halogensubstituted naphthyl	B.	M.P.	Yield	Formula	%Carbon, Found, Reqd.	%Hydrogen, Found, Reqd.	%Nitrogen, Found, Reqd.	%Sulphur, Found, Reqd.				
1-Chloro-2,6-DN-	2,6-DNP	87°	86%	C ₁₁ H ₁₃ O ₂ N ₂ S ₂	43.23	41.80	4.23	13.26	13.33	20.30	20.32	
1,2-Dichloro-4,6-DN-	6-Chloro-2,4-DNP	112°	80	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ O ₂ N ₂ ClS ₂	36.08	37.77	3.61	3.43	12.02	16.24	16.31	
1-Chloro-2-bromo-4,6-DN-	6-Bromo-2,4-DNP	102°	80	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ O ₂ N ₂ BrS ₂	..	..	..	10.60	10.66	16.20	16.24	
1-Chloro-2-iodo-4,6-DN-	6-Iodo-2,4-DNP	178°	85	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ O ₂ N ₂ I ₂	..	..	..	9.44	9.52	14.49	14.51	
1,2-Dichloro-4,6-DN-	6-Chloro-2,4-DNP	116°	83	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ O ₂ N ₂ ClS ₂	38.21	37.77	3.40	3.43	12.11	12.02	16.27	16.31
1,4-Dichloro-2,6-DN-	4-Chloro-2,6-DNP	206°	80	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ O ₂ N ₂ ClS ₂	37.28	37.77	3.41	3.43	11.86	12.02	15.28	16.31
1-Chloro-4,6-DN-2-Me-	6-Methyl-2,4-DNP	126°	75	C ₁₂ H ₁₅ O ₂ N ₂ S ₂	..	..	..	12.88	12.77	16.42	16.45	
1-Chloro-4,6-DN-3-Me-	5-Methyl-2,4-DNP	79°	75	C ₁₂ H ₁₅ O ₂ N ₂ S ₂	44.03	43.76	4.61	4.56	12.70	12.77	16.41	16.45
1-Chloro-2,4,6-TN-4-Me-	4-Methyl-2,6-DNP	86°	80	C ₁₂ H ₁₅ O ₂ N ₂ S ₂	44.42	43.76	4.50	4.56	12.65	12.77	16.43	16.45
1-Chloro-2,4,6-TN-5-Me-	5-Methyl-2,4,6-TNP	136°	86	C ₁₂ H ₁₅ O ₂ N ₂ S ₂	..	..	..	14.94	14.98	17.08	17.11	
1,2,3-Trichloro-4,6-DN-	5,6-Dichloro-2,4-DNP	136°	90	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ O ₂ N ₂ Cl ₂ S ₂	33.01	34.37	2.80	2.86	10.90	10.54	16.60	16.66
2-Chloro-1,3-dibromo-4,6-DN-	5-Bromo-6-chloro-2,4-DNP	143°	86	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ O ₂ N ₂ ClBrS ₂	..	..	..	9.75	9.80	14.08	14.93	
1,6-Dichloro-4,6-DN-5-Me-	6-Chloro-3-methyl-2,4-DNP	136°	80	C ₁₂ H ₁₄ O ₂ N ₂ ClS ₂	39.24	39.61	3.70	3.86	11.58	11.55	17.56	17.61
4-Chloro-1-bromo-2,6-DN-5-Me-	4-Chloro-5-methyl-2,6-DNP	123°	84	C ₁₂ H ₁₄ O ₂ N ₂ ClS ₂	..	..	..	11.51	11.56	17.69	17.61	
1,3-Dichloro-4,6-DN-2-Me-	5-Chloro-6-methyl-2,4-DNP	117°	75	C ₁₂ H ₁₄ O ₂ N ₂ ClS ₂	39.30	39.61	3.81	3.84	11.52	11.55	17.57	17.61
1,2,6-Trichloro-4,6-DN-	3,6-Dibromo-2,4-DNP	246°	68	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ O ₂ N ₂ Br ₂ S ₂	..	..	..	8.94	8.68	13.50	13.53	
1-Chloro-2,5-dibromo-4,6-DN	3,6-Dibromo-2,4-DNP	246°	75	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ O ₂ N ₂ Br ₂ S ₂	..	..	..	8.84	8.68	13.58	13.53	
1-Chloro-2,4,6-DN-naphthalene	2,4-Dinitro-naphthyl	165°	80	C ₁₀ H ₇ O ₂ N ₂ S ₂	48.08	49.31	3.99	4.11	11.48	11.51	17.55	17.68
1,2,5-Trichloro-4,6-DN-	3,6-Dichloro-2,4-DNP	244°	82	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ O ₂ N ₂ Cl ₂ S ₂	..	..	..	10.98	10.94	16.84	16.66	
2,6-Dichloro-1-bromo-4,6-DN-	2,6-Dichloro-2,4-DNP	244°	85	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ O ₂ N ₂ Cl ₂ S ₂	34.91	34.37	2.84	2.86	10.19	10.44	16.63	16.66

* All melting points are uncorrected.

N.B. DN, TN, DNP and TNP refer respectively to dinitro, trinitro, dimitrophenyl, and trinitrophenyl.

HALOGENONITROPHENYL AND NAPHTHYL ESTERS OF *NN*-DIETHYLDITHIOCARBAMIC ACID 81

6-Chloro-2,4-dinitrophenyl ester of *NN*-diethyldithiocarbamic acid inhibited the growth of *Trichophyton mentagrophytes*, *Microsporum canis*, and *Aspergillus niger* at a concentration of 1/1000, whereas 6-methyl-2,4-dinitrophenyl, 5-chloro-6-methyl-2,4-dinitrophenyl and 2,4-dinitronaphthyl esters of *NN*-diethyldithiocarbamic acid inhibited the growth of *Trichophyton mentagrophytes* and *Microsporum canis* at a similar concentration. None of them, however, showed any activity against *Bacillus subtilis*, *Escherichia coli*, *Salmonella typhi*, *Agrobacterium tumefaciens*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Candida albicans*, and *Cryptococcus neoformans*.

General Method for the Preparation of Halogenonitrophenyl and Naphthyl Esters of NN-Diethyldithiocarbamic Acid.—A solution of the halogenopolynitrobenzene (0.01*M*, 20% soln.) in ethanol was added dropwise with stirring to a 10% solution of sodium diethyldithiocarbamate (0.01*M*) in ethanol, cooled to 5° in $\frac{1}{2}$ hr. The reaction mixture was further stirred until the product separated. The temperature of the reaction mixture was kept below 10° during the entire process. The crystals of the esters separating were filtered, washed with water, dried in air, and crystallised from anhydrous ethanol.

These esters are shining crystalline compounds, insoluble in water but dissolve readily in acetone. These are sparingly soluble in methanol and ethanol. Their colour varies from light yellow to orange-yellow.

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